

Legal and Ethical Challenges Related to the Use of Social Media Data and Related Data

CLARIN-PLUS workshop „Creation and Use of Social Media Resources“
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Social Science Data Archive

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Outline

- About the Social Science Data Archive
- About the SERISS project
- WP6: New forms of data: Legal and ethical issues

About the Social Science Data Archive

- Established in 1997
- National repository for social sciences (the only research data repository in Slovenia)
- More than 600 social science surveys
- 700 users yearly
- Member of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives ([CESSDA](#)) and involved in several [international research projects](#) (DwB, Foster, SEEDS, SaW, SERISS ...)

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SYNERGIES FOR EUROPE'S
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES

www.seriss.eu
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A collaboration between:

- European Social Survey (ESS ERIC)
- Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE ERIC)
- Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA AS)
- Generations and Gender Programme (GGP)
- European Values Study
- WageIndicator Survey

cessda

European *Values* Study

 WageIndicator.org

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 654221.

Designed to:

- Strengthen social science research across Europe and beyond by overcoming fragmentation and fostering interoperability, harmonisation and innovation
- Equip social science infrastructures to play a major role in addressing key societal challenges and ensure that national and European policy making is built on a firm socio-economic evidence base
- Promote the value of the social sciences to the wider research community, and policymakers

Achieved by:

- **Addressing key challenges for cross-national data collection** e.g. accurately representing the population, achieving equivalence through translation
- **Breaking down barriers between social science infrastructures** via training and networking events and the development of shared online tools to facilitate harmonised data collection and documentation.
- **Embracing the future of the social sciences** by examining the legal and ethical challenges associated with new forms of data, developing a cross-national probability-based web survey and exploring automated coding for socio-economic variables

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WP6: New forms of data: legal, ethical and quality issues

(Marianne Høgetveit Myhren, Norwegian Social Science Data Services)

6.1 Legal and ethical challenges related to the use of social media data and related data

6.2 Legal, ethical and quality challenges related to the use of administrative data

6.3 Connected curation and quality

6.4 Consent and biomarkers

Legal vs ethical

Legal standards are based on written law.

Ethical standards are based on human rights and wrongs.

Something can be legal but not ethical.

Legal framework

- The new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will replace the former EU Data Protection Directive in May 2018
- Objectives:
 - To protect fundamental rights and freedoms of persons, in particular their right to protect personal data
 - To allow for the free movement of personal data without restrictions and prohibitions for reasons connected with the protection of persons with regard to the processing of personal data.
- Special provisions and important exemptions for archiving and research purposes

Legal questions on Twitter research

- Beurskens, M. (2014): Legal Questions of Twitter Research V: V: Weller, K.; Bruns, A.; Burgess, J.; Mahrt, M.; Puschmann, C.: Twitter and Society. Peter Lang.
- Twitter's general Terms of Services
- Twitter's Rules of the Road prohibit „exporting Twitter content to a datastore as a services or other cloud based service“
- Transparency and reproducibility are fundamental in research
- Twitter disapproves of making Twitter data sets available

Plans for future

- Report on legal, ethical and quality issues of new forms of data
- CLARIN will be one of the case studies presented in the report
- Workshop on informed consent (November/December)

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